

RESURRECTING THE VIOLINO ARPA: A MUSEUM EXHIBITION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a project aimed at digitally resurrecting and presenting the unique Violino Arpa instrument from the collection of The Danish Music Museum, part of the National Museum of Denmark. The project endeavors to create an interactive installation that provides visitors with an understanding of the impact of different violin body designs through co-design. The paper offers a comprehensive examination of the project's development and execution, including a review of relevant literature in the field of interactive museum installations and physical modeling of string instruments. The design, implementation, hardware, software, and challenges encountered, as well as the solutions adopted, are described in detail. Furthermore, an evaluation of the project was conducted by museum personnel at The Danish Music Museum. Observations of the participants revealed that the installation was engaging and interactive. However, some participants found aspects of the installation confusing, while others enjoyed the experience, found it aesthetically pleasing, and perceived clear differences between the sound of the Violino Arpa and the classical violin.

1. INTRODUCTION

Museums have traditionally been spaces for the preservation and display of physical objects. In 1970, Joseph Veach Noble, later to be president of the American Association of Museums, coined the basic responsibilities of every museum: to collect, to conserve, to interpret, and to exhibit [1]. However, in recent years there has been a shift towards a more interactive and experiential approach to museums, known as the *museum paradigm shift*. This shift has been driven by several factors, including advances in technology, changes in visitor expectations, and a desire to make museums more inclusive and relevant to contemporary society [2]. As a result, museums are increasingly incorporating interactive exhibits, virtual reality experiences, and other multimedia elements into their exhibits, as well as rethinking their roles as educational and cultural institutions [3].

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Figure 1: Violino Arpa in The Danish Music Museum.
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The Danish Music Museum (Musikmuseet) is home to a fine example of a Violino Arpa in its collection (Figure 1). This rare and beautiful instrument, also known as the amoeba violin is a unique instrument designed and built by innovative instrument maker, Thomas Zach (1812-1892). The instrument was first presented by Zach at the World's Fair in 1873 in Vienna.

This project aims to digitally resurrect this unique instrument and make it available to the public through an interactive installation that invites museum visitors to become part of the violin-design process to understand the effect of different violin bodies. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the museum installation project, covering all aspects of its development and execution. To provide context and background for the project, the related work in the field will be discussed. The design and implementation of the project will then be described in detail, including details on both hardware and software development, as well as the challenges and solutions encountered during the development process. Finally, the evaluation of the project will be discussed. Through in-depth analysis, this paper aims to provide a thorough understanding of the museum installation project and its execution.

2. RELATED WORK

The emergence of digital technology has profoundly revolutionized many areas, including preservation and restoration practice [4, 5]. The problems of longevity and portability

bility inherent to any physical copy may be superseded by a smart and durable implementation of new digital techniques: in the present case, one may use digital technologies to produce copies of musical instruments. The most straightforward way of digitally preserving the sound of a musical instrument is to make audio recordings. This technique is known as sampling. Recording-based techniques such as sampling maximize the fidelity of the digital copy, but expressivity and playability are somewhat limited (one literally needs a recording for each playing gesture). These techniques cannot be applied to instruments that are severely damaged or in disrepair.

Since high-quality audio samples are usually not available for original historical instruments, physical modeling methods such as digital waveguides [6, 7], modal synthesis techniques [8], and finite difference (FD) methods [9], can be used to digitally recreate the sounds. Historically, digital waveguides and modal synthesis have been the techniques of choice, but recently, due to the advent of low-cost, powerful computers, FD methods have been used to build sophisticated models of acoustical instruments [9]. FD methods employ a direct simulation of the physics of the given instrument and can produce high-quality results, but at the cost of high computational complexity [10]. However, despite their complexity, such methods are now becoming viable for real-time, interactive applications. The Multisensory Experience Lab at Aalborg University Copenhagen has a long tradition of implementing real-time physics-based simulations [11, 12] recently also using FD methods [13, 14].

Building custom musical interfaces is a highly developed discipline in the academic community *New Interfaces for Musical Expression* (NIME)¹. Digital fabrication techniques, such as 3D printing and laser cutting can be used for the construction of musical interfaces, see e.g., [15–18].

3. DESIGN

The design of this project plays a crucial role in its overall functionality. The goal of the design was to create an interactive and visually striking experience for the user, utilizing both the morphing between violin bodies and sensing the movement of the bow. To achieve this, careful consideration was given to the choice of hardware and software to be used, as well as the overall structure and flow of the project. This section will delve into the specific design decisions that were made and the reasoning behind them.

3.1 Concept

All the design of the installation was performed in co-design activities between the authors of this paper and the personnel of the museum. Some researchers are more technically oriented and working on the development of the application, while others are personnel of the museum and experts in what works in a public and pedagogical setting. As the goal of this project was to create an installation inviting

the user to get an understanding of the effect of different violin bodies, it was a logical course of action, firstly, to include a (deconstructed) violin in the design, secondly to design an interface for the user to visually morph between violin bodies and, lastly, to let the user interact with the instrument using a violin bow, as this would build upon already-existing mental models. Moreover, the interactive installation was placed in close proximity to the display case containing the Violino Arpa. A 3D-sketch of the installation is seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Isometric 3D-graphic of the installation. Drawn by Signe Beckmann, Musikmuseet.

On a touch-screen to the left in the installation, the user can, using a slider, morph smoothly between the body of the Violino Arpa and the body of a classical violin (see section 3.2). To hear the sound of the given body, the user must take the violin bow and bow the *Anybody Violin* next to the screen (see section 3.3 and 3.4). When the user moves the bow, a simple melody (Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star) with the corresponding instrument is played back.

3.2 Morphing Bodies

The choice to morph between two violin shapes in this project served several purposes. First, it allowed for a visually striking and aesthetically pleasing transition between the two body shapes, potentially drawing in and engaging the viewer. Second, it allowed for a more seamless transition between the two shapes, rather than a jarring cut or jump between them. This was particularly useful as the two shapes represented distinct violin types, and the morphing transition helped to emphasize the auditory differences between the two. The visual morphing between the two bodies is seen in Figure 4.

3.3 The *Anybody Violin*

It was decided to include a physical violin in the installation. The violin should have no body to visually engage the user in selecting a body on the touchscreen, how the concept of the *Anybody Violin* was born.

A violin was acquired and carefully deconstructed, separating the neck from the body of the instrument, as the neck

¹ <https://www.nime.org/>

of the violin, with no body, was to be incorporated into the physical installation. This was a delicate process, using Dremel and multi-cutter, and required caution to avoid damaging the neck. The violin neck needed to be stripped for paint to prepare it for varnish. The neck was sanded, working up to fine grit to achieve a smooth finish. After the neck was sanded, a coat of eight layers of dark shellac was applied for protection and finish.

Figure 4: Smooth morphing between violin body shapes.

3.4 Enhanced Bow

One aspect of the implementation of this project involved attaching an accelerometer to the violin bow to track its movement. In order to do this, an enclosure for the ac-

celerometer was designed in OpenSCAD², a software platform for creating 3D models. The enclosure was designed to securely hold the accelerometer in place while also allowing it to move and rotate with the bow as the bow was used. Finally, it was 3D printed using an Ultimaker 3 printer³. The enclosure was then attached to the violin bow by incorporating the bow's screw into the design as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Accelerometer in a 3D-printed enclosure mounted to the violin bow.

This allowed the accelerometer to be mounted onto the bow stably and reliably, ensuring that it would be able to accurately track the movement of the bow. The use of a 3D-printed enclosure for the accelerometer allowed for a high level of customization and precision in the mounting process. It also allowed for the creation of a compact and lightweight design, ensuring that the overall setup of the violin and bow would not be overly cumbersome or bulky.

The final installation installed at The Danish Music Museum is seen in Figure 3.

² <https://openscad.org>

³ <https://ultimaker.com>

Figure 3: The final installation at The Danish Music Museum.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

In the following section, the steps taken to implement the installation are described. A detailed breakdown of the hardware and software used will also be provided.

4.1 Technical Setup

The technical side of the installation can be considered in three interplaying parts: the selection of violin body on the touchscreen, the tracking of the interaction with the bow, and the physical *Anybody Violin*. In Figure 6, the setup is visualized.

Figure 6: Technical diagram of the installation.

4.2 Interpolating Between Shapes

To implement the morphing visual element of the project, the shapes of the violins were first traced using Adobe Illustrator. This provided digital representations of the violins that could be easily manipulated and edited. ArrayLists of vectors were then filled with the vertices of the traced violin shapes. These vectors served as the points that would be interpolated to create the morphing effect. A matrix of vectors of size numSteps, numOfVertices was created to store the intermediate steps of the morphing process, with each row representing a specific step and each column representing a specific vertex. Interpolation between each corresponding vertex was performed, calculating the intermediate positions of the vertices between the two violin shapes at each step of the morphing process. The correct index/step was then calculated based on the user's input on the screen, allowing the morphing process to be controlled and customized by the viewer. Finally, all vectors were drawn for the current index/step, rendering the intermediate shapes of the violins based on the stored vectors in the matrix and creating the illusion of a seamless transition between the two shapes. The process is outlined in Figure 7.

4.3 Physical Modeling

Modeling the sound of the Violino Arpa was divided into two parts: strings and body. It was decided to use the Virtual Studio Technology (VST) *SWAM Violin* by Audio

Figure 7: Diagram of the process of morphing between violin bodies.

Modeling⁴ for the string sound as the VST offers a highly realistic violin sound. To ensure the cleanest string sound from the VST the *Electric Violin 1* preset was used, ensuring minimal interference of the instrument's body.

The physical model of the body was implemented as a thin plate also known as the Kirchhoff model with losses based on an implementation by Kaloumenou et. al [19]. The partial differential equation describing the transverse displacement, $u = u(x, y, t)$ (in m) in continuous time is seen below [19, 20]:

$$\rho H \partial_t^2 u = -D \Delta \Delta u - 2\sigma_0 \rho H \partial_t u + 2\sigma_1 \rho H \partial_t \Delta u \quad (1)$$

where $D = EH^3/12(1 - \nu^2)$ (in $kg \cdot m^2 \cdot s^{-2}$) is the bending stiffness of the plate and results from the Young's Modulus (in Pa) of the plate thickness H (in m) and the dimensionless Poisson's Ratio ν [20]. Loss coefficients σ_0 is the frequency-independent (in s^{-1}) and σ_1 is the frequency-dependent (in m^2/s) damping coefficients [20]. Furthermore, clamped boundary conditions are used at the edges of the plate [19].

The model was discretized using finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) methods. This method involves solving the differential equations that govern the behavior of the sound wave in order to generate a realistic and accurate simulation of the sound. The discretized equation is seen below [19, 20]:

$$\delta_{tt} u_{l,m}^n = -\kappa^2 \delta_{\Delta} \delta_{\Delta} u_{l,m}^n - 2\sigma_0 \delta_t \cdot u_{l,m}^n + 2\sigma_1 \delta_t \cdot \delta_{\Delta} u_{l,m}^n, \quad (2)$$

with

$$\kappa = \sqrt{\frac{D}{\rho H}} \quad (3)$$

⁴ <https://audiomodeling.com/swam-engine/>

As implemented by Kaloumenou et. al, the plate is "sculpted" to the shape of the body of the Violino Arpa using a staircase approximation, requiring that boundary conditions are satisfied at the edges of the plate [19]. This is achieved by having two neighboring points in both x and y directions set to zero [19]. Based on an image of the body of the Violino Arpa, a shape was traced and used to select the grid points of interest for the plate by setting all other grid points to zero [19]. Finally, a stability condition of the plate is given by [21]:

$$h_p \geq h_{p,min} = 2\sqrt{k \left(\sigma_{1,p} + \sqrt{\kappa_p^2 + \sigma_{1,p}^2} \right)} \quad (4)$$

4.4 Tracking & Audio Playback

For the playback of the audio in the installation, a BELA⁵ was used. Using a BELA for the playback of audio output and tracking accelerometer data in this project offered several benefits. Using the BELA for audio playback allowed for precise and reliable control over the audio output, as the small computer prioritizes the audio thread. The BELA is known for its ultra-low latency and can be programmed to trigger the playback of specific audio files at precise times, allowing for a high level of synchronization between the audio and any other elements of the project, such as the morphing visual.

5. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the approach and strategies used in the development of the installation. In this project, co-design was adopted as the method of choice in collaboration with museum personnel. The following section provides a detailed description of the co-design process.

The development of the installation involved active participation and collaboration from the museum personnel throughout the design and development phases. Our approach was based on the following steps:

1. *Initial consultations*: A series of meetings with the museum personnel were conducted to understand their requirements and gather information about the objectives, audience, and physical space for the installation.
2. *Ideation and prototyping*: The initial design concepts and ideas were developed through a series of brainstorming and sketching. These ideas were then discussed and refined with the collaborators from the museum as well as relevant professionals from Aalborg University Copenhagen.
3. *Informal testing*: After developing the prototypes, informal testing was conducted at Aalborg Universitet Copenhagen to gather feedback and to shed light

on eventual design flaws. This was done to ensure that the overall functionality and usability of the installation were maintained. Furthermore, significant changes to the design based on feedback were discussed with the collaborators at the museum.

4. *Implementation and evaluation*: After settling on the final design, it was implemented and installed at the museum. The implementation of the installation was primarily performed at Aalborg University Copenhagen. However, the components required for the assembly of the installation, such as the backplate, mounts for the violin parts, etc., were manufactured by the personnel at The Danish National Museum. The installation was evaluated through a series of interviews with museum guests, aimed at evaluating the usability and the perceived intent of the installation, as described in the following section.

6. EVALUATION

This section covers the evaluation of the installation conducted at The Danish Music Museum. A series of short interviews with museum guests were conducted at the museum by museum personnel. There were 21 participants aged between 10 and 68 years (Mdn 42.0, SD 15.2). Participants visited museums between 0 and 36 times a year. (Mdn 1.5, SD 0.71). Before their visit that day, 42.9% of the participants indicated that they had prior knowledge of The Danish Music Museum. The participants were selected after voluntarily interacting with the installation. Museum personnel observed the interaction between the guest and the installation, and invited the guest to answer the following questions in a short interview while noting down the answers:

- Which words can describe your experience?
- To what extent were you motivated throughout the experience?
- What do you think was good/bad?
- What do you think was difficult/easy/too easy?
- Did you experience the involvement of multiple senses during the experience?
- Did you experience the installation alone or with others?
- Did you perceive a connection between the object in the display case and the experience?
- Would you expect there to be other similar installations in the exhibition?
- We have a hypothesis that you can get closer to objects by conveying them in new ways. What do you think about this?
- If you had to give us one piece of advice for the next time we build an installation at the museum, what would it be?
- Is there anything else you would like to tell us?

The evaluation revealed several key aspects that are worth noting.

⁵ <https://bela.io/>

Observing the participants interact with the installation revealed that guests spend up to four minutes interacting (Mdn 2.0, SD 1.3). During the observation, it was observed that the installation was frequently engaged by multiple guests simultaneously. In certain configurations, one individual would operate the bow while another would select the violin body on the screen. Additionally, at times, up to four guests would engage with the installation concurrently. Several participants clearly understood the purpose of the installation and enjoyed the experience of hearing different violin bodies. Statements such as: "It became fuller with the shape. A regular violin is sharper/ not unfolded." and "It's funny how sound changes with shape.". Other participants found it difficult to perceive an auditory difference between the sound of the Violino Arpa and a classical violin. This is seen in the statements: "Not sure if there was a difference in the nuances. Not obvious." and "I couldn't hear a difference."

It was clear from the interviews that some participants found it confusing that the movement of the violin bow would trigger a melody instead of "playing" like a real violin. This is clear from statements from some museum guests: "I thought I heard myself playing, but there was already a melody" and "Funny, but it just played 'twinkle twinkle'. Expected to be able to strike notes on the violin.", indicating the confusion of some users. Through observations, it was additionally found that, especially, violin players found it confusing that the behavior was not identical to an acoustic violin. Several participants stated that the violin started playing disconnected from their interaction stating that they "tried to see if it was me or that one - it was the screen playing for me" and "Didn't really get it, played without me doing anything."

While results indicate frustration among some users, others found enjoyment in the interactive concept with statements such as: "Pleased that it worked out - good experience.", "Nice to be able to do something in an exhibition, active, make something. Interactive is cool." and "Cool with sound, interaction, so you don't just go and look at things.". Furthermore, it was observed that even small children found the installation enjoyable. Interaction of the youngest children often included wearing the headset and interacting with the bow, without paying attention to the screen for selecting the violin body. This aligns with a statement from a participant: "Nice that my 12-year-old and 5-year-old can have fun in their own way.". The participants, moreover, generally expressed how they were very pleased with the aesthetics of the installation with statements such as: "Visually pretty, aesthetic, appetizing to look at".

When asked if the participants perceived a connection between the installation and the display case, the majority stated that the connection between the real Violino Arpa and the interactive installation was clear. This is backed up by statements such as: "Yes, the sound ties them together", "Yes, easy with the shape. Very visible, had seen

the shape on postcards." and "Yes, we saw it in the display case before".

7. DISCUSSION

Several elements of the Violino Arpa installation project merit thorough discussion in this paper. These aspects include the use of accelerometers in capturing the violin playing movements, the durability and stability of the installation over time, and the auditory validity of the violin sounds generated for the installation.

The use of accelerometers to track the movement of the violin bow was an intuitive choice to measure if the user is interacting with the violin bow, due to the nature of accelerometers. While offering a simple way of measuring acceleration, thorough filtering of the data was necessary to track the movement accurately. While providing good tracking, the audio can be triggered if the bow is moved in the vertical direction when bowing is not intended, as it is hard to differentiate between purposive bowing and similar movement of the bow. To solve this issue, it was considered adding a second sensor, such as a pickup on the strings, to the installation ensuring that bowing, and not other types of movement, is performed. While potentially enhancing the sensing of interaction, the simplicity of the technical back-end of the installation was prioritized. As documented through the evaluation, several participants were confused with the installation playing regardless of their interaction. This indicated that the sensibility of the accelerometer was too high, triggering the violin melody too easily. As a result, significant efforts were focused on improving the filtering of accelerometer data after the evaluation to enhance the quality of the interaction measurements.

As the installation will be installed in a public museum, it is worth discussing the durability of the installation. As described in section 4.1, the installation can be considered in three interplaying parts: the selection of the violin body on the touchscreen, the tracking of the interaction with the bow, and the physical *Anybody Violin*. While the touchscreen interface and the physical *Anybody Violin* are considered to be very reliable and durable, the bow could wear over time. The nature of the violin is relatively fragile, prone to breaking or flossing if mistreated, and as this part is to be handled by museum guests, it can be assumed that it could need replacement over time. As the enclosure of the accelerometer is built around the bow screw, this allows for plug-and-play replacement of the bow.

Finally, the auditory validity of the generated Violino Arpa sound should be discussed. Due to its rarity, and to preserve the old instruments, no audio recordings of the Violino Arpa exist, why only first-hand encounters stating that the sound is "nasal and unclear"⁶ can be used as a reference. The generated Violino Arpa sound from this project has a clear nasal character and lacks high-end com-

⁶ <https://www.mim.be/en/collection-piece/violino-arpa>

pared to recordings of a classical violin. Through an informal listening session with museum personnel, it was determined that the quality of the generated sounds met a satisfactory level when compared to the reports from individuals who had heard the Violino Arpa being played in the past. These evaluations, based on subjective listening experiences, suggest that the installation effectively captures the distinctive qualities of the original instrument. While capturing the original sound of the Violino Arpa, some participants reported not being able to distinguish any auditory variation between the two instruments, indicating that the differences are relatively subtle. As some participants heard clear differences, this could also indicate that musical background, training, etc., could affect how/if the differences are perceived.

8. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper has discussed a project aimed at digitally resurrecting and presenting the unique Violino Arpa instrument from the collection of The Danish Music Museum. An interactive installation that provided visitors with an understanding of the impact of different violin body designs through participatory design was developed. The paper has provided a comprehensive examination of the project's development and execution, including the design, implementation of hardware and software, challenges, and solutions encountered. The evaluation of the Violino Arpa installation project conducted at The Danish Music Museum provided valuable insights into the user experience of the installation. Observations of the participants revealed that the installation was engaging and interactive. However, some participants found aspects of the installation confusing, while others enjoyed the experience, found it aesthetically pleasing, and perceived clear differences between the sound of the Violino Arpa and the classical violin. Nonetheless, the majority of participants perceived a clear connection between the installation and the Violino Arpa in the display case. In conclusion, the project describes a unique approach to bringing a historical instrument to life through physical modeling and interactivity, providing an immersive experience for visitors to the museum.

Acknowledgments

We thank Marius Onofrei for his contributions to the implementation of the Violino Arpa model. His expertise and support were invaluable to the project's success. We also thank Signe Beckmann for her help in designing the visual installation and Louis Lange Wollesen for his detailed work on making mounts for the various violin parts for the installation. Additionally, we would like to acknowledge the remaining museum personnel who have been extremely helpful throughout the project. Their support is greatly appreciated. We thank The Augustinus Foundation for funding the project presented in this paper.

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